

NESTING AND DEFORMATION IN THE COMPACTION OF PLAIN-WEAVE WOVEN FABRICS

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SUMMARY

This paper presents experimental and analytical results for the compaction of a carbon plain-weave fabric. A model similar to that presented by Chen and Chou [1] was modified for fabrics with a gap between the yarns and used with beam bending theory to predict the compressive behaviour of the fabric. A comparative study on the degree of nesting was evaluated using the model and showed that up to 1.8% variation in fibre volume fraction could be realised for the experimental range of nesting found in the samples. The beam bending theory was applied to the second compression mode and the results compare reasonably well with experimental data.

KEYWORDS

Compaction, carbon plain-weave fabric, compressibility, preform, nesting

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composite structures usually have high fibre volume fractions in the range of 50-70%. Compaction of dry fabric preforms is required to achieve this fibre volume fraction for liquid moulding processes such as resin transfer moulding, resin film infusion, and vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding, where liquid resin is infused through the preform via positive pressure and/or vacuum.

A significant amount of research has been devoted to the investigation of the compressibility of various fibre reinforcements and a large number of publications [1-11] can be found on this topic from the literature of both textiles and composites. Compaction of plain-weave fabrics has been reported by Chen and Chou [1,2], Pearce and Summerscales [3], Saunders [9], and Lekakou [10]. Yurgatis [11] characterised the yarn shape for plain-weave composites.

The compaction of a plain-weave fabric results in yarn flattening, reduction of pores and gaps among the fibres and yarns, elastic deformation, and nesting of layers and interlayer packing [2]. In the first compression mode, the fibre cloths nest closer by slipping under compression. There is also a slight flattening of the yarn bundle. In the second compression mode, the fibre yarns are deformed by decreasing the amplitude of yarn waveform in which case the thickness of the individual plies is reduced. In the third compression mode, the fibre yarns are flattened further [9]. However, the compaction pressures are above the range used in most preforming processes for this mode.

Theoretical compressibility models for the second compression mode have been proposed by several researchers based upon beam theory [12-15]. This paper focuses on the bending deformation stage and compares experimental results to beam theory for a variety of nested configurations.

Mechanical tests were carried out on an assembly of plain-weave dry fabrics using an MTS machine. Yarn flattening was determined using a stereo microscope on the compressed fabrics. The degree of nesting was determined using photomicrographs.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The carbon plain-weave fabric was from SP Systems, RC200P, HS-3k fibre, 200 tex, 4.9 ends, areal weight of 195 g/m², and a thickness of 0.25 mm.

The preforms consisted of four layers of fabrics stacked in the 0° direction. The compaction tests were conducted on a 250 kN MTS machine (within the 25 kN loading range). A 25 mm thick steel circular platen of 150 mm in diameter was fitted to the top of the MTS machine while another circular platen of 200 mm in diameter was placed on the base. The 175 mm diameter reinforcements were compacted between these two platens.

It should be noted that the experimental apparatus, including the platens and the MTS machine, deforms under the compaction load. Such deformation was excluded when determining the thickness of the compacted specimen from the crosshead displacement recorded. This is particularly important when the thickness of the specimen is small. Zeroing the displacement at zero load can also cause error due to small load fluctuations, hence the displacement was zeroed at a known load. In the present work, the zero offset point and the deformation of the apparatus was determined by an apparatus compliance test.

During the compression test, the bottom platen was moved up until the load reached 50 kPa then was subsequently advanced by 100 kPa intervals from 100 kPa to 700 kPa (at approximately 1.0 mm/min or less). At each step, the movement of the bottom platen was stopped, and both the load and displacement were recorded after 5 minutes to allow for the relaxation of fiber network [16].

Some samples were injected with a cyanoacrylate adhesive (Loctite 401) on the edge after relaxation at a specified load. The adhesive impregnated the edge of the dry fabric stack via capillary flow. The section was then subsequently infused with resin and mounted for photomicrographs.

The stereo microscope was also used to measure the non-compacted and compacted yarn width and spacing. This method allowed for several data points to be measured for each compaction pressure.

COMPRESSION TESTING: RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The results of the compaction tests were processed to determine the relationship between the compaction pressure, p , and the fiber volume fraction V_f . For a circular compacting platen, the compaction pressure can be calculated as:

$$p = \frac{F}{\pi R^2} \quad (1)$$

where F is the load measured and R is the radius of the platen.

V_f is calculated using the following formula [9]:

$$V_f = \frac{AN}{\rho t} \quad (2)$$

where N is the number of layers, A is the areal weight of the specimen, ρ is the density of the carbon fibre (= 1780 g/m³), and t is the thickness of specimen under compaction.

It has been suggested that the compaction response of fibre reinforcements can be expressed by the following two-parameter power model representing the fiber volume fraction as a function of the compaction pressure [16]:

$$V_f = kp^m \quad (3)$$

where k and m are the parameters to be determined; k and m can be referred to as the initial fiber volume fraction (fiber volume fraction achieved at the unit compaction pressure) and the stiffening index respectively. It should be noted that a larger m represents a slower stiffening behavior.

Regression analysis was conducted to fit the experimental compaction results to the power model. The parameters obtained are listed in Table 1. The experimental results for the carbon plain-weave fabric are shown in Figure 1. Good agreement was observed between the two tests of the reinforcement and the power model fit.

Figure 2 shows the yarn straightening between 300 kPa to 700 kPa during compaction.

Table 1. Fitted parameters for pressure in kPa

Reinforcement	k	m
Carbon plain-weave, 4 layers	0.337	0.0732

Figure 1. Static Compaction of 4 ply Plain-Weave Carbon Fabric

Figure 2. The photo on the right shows straighter 0° fibres: a) 300 kPa, b) 700 kPa

YARN DEFORMATION

The measured warp and weft yarn widths were averaged and reported in Table 2 for different compaction pressures for the carbon fabric. The yarn width initially increased and then remained constant over the second compression mode range, which is in good agreement with the results presented previously by Saunders [9]. Hence, the assumption of a constant beam width during Mode 2 bending is appropriate.

Table 2. Stereo microscope measurements of carbon yarn flattening

Pressure (kPa)	0	200	300	400	700	900
Warp Yarn Width (mm)/ (STD)	1.648 (0.075)	1.657 (0.053)	1.712 (0.044)	1.668 (0.085)	1.669 (0.075)	1.699 (0.068)
Weft Yarn Width (mm)/ (STD)	1.693 (0.084)	1.765 (0.066)	1.702 (0.082)	1.760 (0.087)	1.770 (0.075)	1.767 (0.054)
Average Yarn Width (mm)	1.672	1.708	1.706	1.713	1.720	1.735

NESTING

The photomicrographs of specimens compacted at 300, 500, and 700 kPa were used to determine the degree of nesting. The edge of one yarn was measured with respect to the edge of a yarn in the next layer to determine the degree of nesting as shown in Figure 3.

The degree of nesting is determined as:

$$\frac{d}{(a + s/2)} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

where a is half of the yarn width, d is the tow shift, and s is the spacing between the yarns. The baseline values for a , and s were measured from the photomicrographs and averaged for each compaction pressure.

Figure 3. Determination of nesting

Table 3 summarises the measurements. The experimental results showed a range from 41 to 76% nesting, with an average of 57%.

Table 3. Nesting measurements

Image Position	Specimen Compaction Pressure (kPa)	Ave Nesting (%)	Std Dev	Ave Nesting Outer Layers (%)	Ave Nesting Inner Layers (%)	Overall Ave (%)	Overall Std Dev
1	300	69.3	19.1	57.7	56.4	57.0	22.0
2	300	73.3	10.9				
3	300	76.3	13.5				
1	500	41.3	25.3				
2	500	52.1	27.7				
3	500	45.8	30.4				
1	700	45.2	10.6				
2	700	43.0	13.5				
3	700	67.1	14.4				

MODEL

The linear region of the compaction curve (Mode 2) starting at P_o and V_{fo} as shown in Figure 1 can be attributed to the bending deformation of the fibres.

In reference [2], a micro-mechanical model was used for predicting the compaction behaviour of a plain-weave fabric. This model includes the following assumptions:

- The unit cell repeats in the plane of the fabric, which is infinite in extent.
- The yarn is treated as a transversely isotropic solid, i.e. the fibres in the yarn are highly compacted.
- The external compressive force is applied uniformly on the fabric preform.
- The elastic deformation of the fabric takes place only in its thickness direction, i.e., neglecting its in-plane deformation.

- During the compaction process, the yarn shape deforms, but the yarn cross-sectional area remains unchanged, i.e. there is a constant yarn packing fraction.

The elastic deformation has been described as follows [2]. At first, the compressive force acts at the peaks of the upper and lower surfaces of the fabric. As the compressive force increases, elastic deformation of the fabric extends, and the thickness of the fabric preform decreases while the fibre volume fraction increases. Also, the external forces are distributed over an increasing contacting area. The yarn cross-sectional area consists of a central rectangular area and two sides bounded by sinusoidal curves (Figure 4a) as described by [2]. It is assumed that the gap between the yarns in this paper does not significantly alter the yarn area. This contacting area expands as the external force increases. When the force reaches a certain value, the fabric cannot be further compressed and the yarn cross-section approaches a rectangle (Figure 4b).

Detailed derivations for Equations 5, and 6 are shown by Chen and Chou in [1]. The radius of contacting area, x_o , (Figure 4a) can be determined as:

$$x_o = \frac{2ar_z}{4(\pi - 2)(2h_y - r_z)} \quad (0 \leq r_z \leq r_{z \max}) \quad (5)$$

Figure 4. (a) yarn cross-sectional area during compression (b) maximum limiting yarn cross-sectional area

where a is half the yarn width, r_z is the thickness reduction per layer, and $2h_y$ is the layer thickness at V_{f0} .

The moment of inertia of one-half of the yarn cross-sectional area with respect to the y-axis is given below:

$$I_y = \frac{4a}{288\pi} \left[2h_y + \frac{\pi}{2(\pi - 2)} r_z \right] (2h_y - r_z)^2 \quad (0 \leq r_z \leq r_{z \max}) \quad (6)$$

Because of the symmetry of the plain-weave fabric, one yarn can be modelled as a beam that extends from below one yarn to above the next yarn. The load distribution for the beam is shown for maximum nesting between two layers within platens and for a random-nested multilayer case in Figure 5. It can be seen that infinite load is required to deflect the beam as it approaches maximum nesting.

Figure 5. Micro-mechanical model for a) maximum nesting between two-layers, and b) random nesting, multiple layers

The solution to the simplified micro-mechanical model for the non-nested two-layer case is:

$$F = \frac{r_z 48EI_y}{(3L(x_o^2 - a^2) + (a^3 - x_o^2))} \quad (7)$$

where E is the fibre modulus. The compaction pressure is determined by:

$$P = \frac{F}{(2a + s)^2} \quad (8)$$

For maximum nesting between two layers the solution to the simplified micro-mechanical model is:

$$F = \frac{r_z 96EI_y}{(3L(x_o^2 - a^2) + (a^3 - x_o^3))} \quad (9)$$

The solution for the random-nested multi-layer case is:

$$F = \frac{r_z 48EI_y}{(6L(e^2 + d^2 - 0.5a^2) + (a^3 - 4e^3 - 4d^3))} \quad (10)$$

Figure 6 shows the predictions of the multi-layer model for different nesting configurations. This model indicates that difference in fibre volume fraction can be as high as 4% when comparing non-nested to maximum-nested configurations for a given load. However, the difference in fibre volume fraction is approximately 1.8% for the experimental range of nesting from 41 to 76%.

The predictions of the model (for two surface layers at 57.7% and two internal layers at 56.4% nesting) are compared to the experimental data power model in Figure 7. An alpha correction factor α of 0.989 was multiplied with the modulus, E , in Equations 9 and 10 to fit the model to the experimental results. This factor adjusts for the assumption that the yarn is a transversely isotropic solid.

The experimental results are slightly non-linear and this may be due to slight slippage at the fibre cross-overs or the slight increase in tow width with increasing pressure. However, the linear model can predict the fibre volume fraction within 1% (for ~400 to 800 kPa).

Figure 6. Model results for various nesting configurations

Figure 7. Carbon plain-weave bending model versus experimental data power model

CONCLUSIONS

From the work presented the following conclusions can be made:

- The compaction test of fibre reinforcements can be conducted using a simple set-up on an MTS testing machine with reasonable accuracy and consistency as long as careful attention is used to determine the experimental apparatus compliance and the zero offset.
- The compaction behaviour of the carbon plain-weave fabric was well represented by the two-parameter power model.
- The fibre yarn initially flattens during compaction, then the width remains constant during a significant portion of the compaction curve, until higher pressures cause further flattening. Hence it is a reasonable assumption to assume a constant beam width for the bending model.
- The assumption that the yarn is a transversely isotropic solid is reasonable in that very little adjustment was required to fit the model to the experimental results.
- Nesting varied from 41 to 76% in the experimental specimens with an average of 57% nesting.
- Based on the experimental nesting range, the model predicts that variations in nesting can change the fibre volume fraction for a given load up to 1.8%.

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